

CO-BOLD

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Keywords

AI Literacy, Algorithmic Bias, Business Ethics, Ethical Decision-making, Gender Studies, Media Literacy, Moral Resoluteness, Responsible AI

Introduction

CO-BOLD was developed at Leuphana University in Lüneburg to address the main reasons why people often fail to detect and address ethical problems in the usage of artificial intelligence (AI). In this digital single-player game, players slip into the role of a quality assurance manager at a large tech company. Their mission is to assess the quality of an innovative AI assistant for investment consultants, *CO-BOLD*, before it is delivered to a large bank. While their team controls the design and performance of the AI, players learn to recognize eight ethical risks and problems common to AI applications. Moreover, they learn to assess the quality of AI applications across eight quality dimensions and to adopt a professional-skeptic stance in evaluating them. Finally, the game challenges learners to speak up and address ethical problems with AI against business pressures.

The game was primarily developed for students of business administration and information science. However, it has also been used in multidisciplinary courses on artificial intelligence, and students of other disciplines, e.g., psychology or sustainability science, have found it accessible.

Facts

Release date:	2023
Developer:	Johannes Katsarov, Tim Wagenbach, Oguzhan Demir, Paul Drews, Hannah Trittin-Ulbrich
Game type:	Digital game
Number of players:	1+ (can be played in classes with hundreds of students).
Format:	Asynchronous
Time frame:	2–3 hours
Languages:	English, German
Environment:	Desktop, learning management system, or online
Material:	Free educational materials available online
Price:	Free

Resonance & Criticism

In 2024, CO-BOLD received an “Innovations That Inspire” award from the Association to Advance Collegiate Schools of Business (AACSB, 2024), the global standard-setting body for business education. So far, CO-BOLD has been tested at the Universities of Kiel, Linz, and Lüneburg, as well as RWTH Aachen, with more than 2,000 students in total. On average, students from Lüneburg reported that they could identify with their role relatively well, that the situations were realistic, and that the experience was rewarding. With a couple of exceptions, the game's usability was considered good. On average, students also agreed that they learned a lot about ethical problems and the risks of artificial intelligence from playing CO-BOLD. 90% of students from Linz had a (very) positive experience with CO-BOLD, and 75% (strongly) agreed that they had gained a deeper understanding of AI-related risks and challenges from playing the game. On average, a small percentage of students (about 5-10%) have disliked the game, partially due to bugs and, in some cases, also due to a dislike of game-based learning. The most frequently requested improvement was a voice-over, due to the large amount of text; some students struggled to maintain their focus for 2-3 hours of gameplay. The voice-over and other improvements, including a better save function, have been made recently.

Game principle & Process

In CO-BOLD, players slip into the role of a newly appointed quality manager at a big tech company. The game can be played individually or in small groups. Players' assignment is to control the design and performance of a new AI assistant called “CO-BOLD” before it is delivered to a major bank. In an introductory meeting, players learn how CO-BOLD is supposed to assist bankers in helping clients to make investment decisions by subtly prompting bankers to ask the right kinds of questions. Players then have a tight deadline to assess diverse quality aspects of CO-BOLD. Each day, they can appoint their two assistants to a wide variety of quality assessments (see Figure 1). This investigative learning strategy was chosen because research suggests that it could be invaluable in promoting awareness of complex ethical issues (Katsarov, 2023).

Players lack the time to pursue all possible investigations, which forces them to prioritize their actions strategically and scrutinize the evidence that they find. This mechanism makes it meaningful for learners to understand the scientific and statistical concepts shared through dialogues and to apply them in imagining possible risks. Moreover, players receive three types of points as immediate 360° feedback during the game. This feedback mechanism challenges players to (1) identify correct statements about AI, (2) display good leadership behavior, and (3) act responsibly by upholding ethical principles. By winning or losing points, in combination with responses from the game's characters, players learn whether they applied concepts correctly. At the end of the game, players can propose several improvements to CO-BOLD. However, to persuade their boss and the development team, they need to propose appropriate measures and present sound arguments. The game culminates in one of four

endings, depending on whether the AI assistant's two major flaws were addressed appropriately.

Figure 1. Overview pages and example gameplay screen from CO-BOLD, a digital serious game on ethical risk assessment and responsible use of artificial intelligence in business contexts. © Johannes Katsarov, Paul Drews, and Hannah Trittin-Ulbrich. All rights reserved for the creators.

Learning objectives & Educational fields of application

CO-BOLD was designed to educate learners about eight general risks in using AI (O’Neil, 2016; Coeckelbergh, 2020): First, it demonstrates how algorithmic bias occurs and how it can lead to a (1) reinforcement of injustice and (2) exclusion from opportunity, ensuing (3) harm to some groups (economic harm, in this case). Second, the game illuminates how (4) the lack of transparency in how AI generates seemingly good outputs (“black box” problem), and (5) a diffusion of responsibility for AI-supported decision-making can lead to (6) an over-reliance on AI (suspension of judgment) in developers and users: problems in the dataset and goal-setting of AI systems may be ignored. This makes people prone to ignore the (7) possibility of errors, (8) manipulation, and deception. Players gradually learn about these risks, how and why they can occur through their investigation. This way, CO-BOLD aims to instill a professional-skeptic attitude in players, a critically constructive stance towards using AI for good purposes while keeping its limitations in mind (cf. Hurtt 2010). Concretely, they are trained to consider eight quality dimensions of AI (Tamboli, 2019) during their investigation, which guide their search. Sensitivity to AI-related risks is also coupled with training in speak-up competences (moral

resoluteness), which are developed throughout the game as players address diverse risks and problems despite resistance from the developers (Gentile, 2010).

Educators can use a package of freely available teaching materials to implement CO-BOLD in the classroom. Since the game takes a long time to play, it is ideally assigned as homework. Completion of this assignment can be tracked through learning management systems like Moodle, which support CO-BOLD, or through reflective questions students must answer after playing the game. After playing CO-BOLD, the first phase of the debriefing should focus on allowing players to reflect on the experience. For example, they can select emojis that best represent their impression from playing the game. In a subsequent analysis, think-pair-share could be used to have learners reflect on the question: what ethical risks of AI does the game address? The slides can be used for the final transfer phase of debriefing. They illustrate how different value dimensions must be considered in developing and using AI (Floridi et al., 2018) and present real-world cases to learners, including large-scale government scandals. Generally, educators should have played the game once before using it in class and understand the main ways the scenario can unfold (see the teaching materials). The insights from the scenario can then be used to dive deeper into questions of AI and business ethics, as well as moral psychology. Different debriefing activities are recommended for small and large groups.

Effectiveness

In a quasi-experiment with 95 management students, CO-BOLD yielded substantial effects on students' ability to recognize seven ethical risks related to AI during the final exam. On average, students identified 4 of these problems in the exam, whereas a comparison group without AI ethics training identified only 1-2 issues. It is still unclear, however, how much of this learning can be attributed to the game itself, since it was combined with other learning activities. In an online experiment with 100 business and IT professionals, no comparable effects could be found, despite participants' belief that they had learned a lot from playing the game. This finding is probably due to the qualitative test used: several participants reported not making an effort to describe all the risks and issues in the written test when there was no incentive. Based on players' general feedback, participants appear to learn a great deal about AI ethics through gameplay. However, combining the game with a structured debriefing and embedding it in additional activities probably adds significant value. We hope to publish the results from our diverse experiments with the game soon.

Potentially problematic aspects

A significant challenge in using CO-BOLD for purposes of teaching is its length and the large amount of text. Some students may not have the capacity to focus on the game for its entire duration in one sitting. Hence, we recommend assigning the game as homework and informing students that it can be played in several sittings. Also, the game requires a relatively

new computer to run at normal speed. Allowing players to team up in groups while playing the game is a helpful solution here. Care has been taken to design CO-BOLD for all ages. Although it covers issues like algorithmic bias against women and foreigners and possible harm to different target groups, the story avoids violence and heavy forms of discrimination, focusing on an ironic portrayal of microaggressions instead. Due to the heavy reliance on text and the need for players to logically understand and apply scientific and statistical concepts (e.g., spurious correlations), the game is probably only appropriate for learners 14 and older. Players with visual impairments will need support with reading texts during the game.

Reviewer(s): Lucian Alikhani, Saskia Sterzl

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